

DETECTING LUNAR IMPACT FLASHES WITH ESA LUMIO CUBESAT: mission updates at phase C

S. Sughi¹, F. Ferrari¹, F. Topputo¹, A. Bellanca¹, C. Giordano¹, P. Panicucci¹, A. Pizzetti¹, D. Koschny², E. Ammannito³, A. Zinzi³, R. Moissl⁴, ¹Department of Aerospace Science and Technology, Politecnico di Milano (sabrina.sughi@polimi.it), ²Technical University of Munich, Germany, ³Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, ⁴European Space Agency

Introduction: The Earth–Moon system is continuously exposed to a flux of meteoroids and micrometeoroids that impact the surfaces of both bodies, posing potential hazards to our planet and to future lunar missions. Lacking an atmosphere, the Moon experiences a particularly high frequency of impacts, typically from objects ranging from a few tens of grams to several kilograms each day. With the renewed interest in robotic and human lunar exploration, this elevated impact rate becomes increasingly significant, especially for missions involving long-duration presence on the lunar surface. Moreover, the meteoroid flux at the Moon and at Earth’s surface are strongly linked, making measurements in the former environment essential for refining current impacts models of both celestial objects, with implications in planetary defense, mission design, and in our understanding in meteor science.

The Lunar Meteoroid Impact Observer (LUMIO) is a CubeSat mission designed to observe, quantify, and characterize lunar meteoroid impacts by detecting their flashes on the Moon far side when impacting the surface [1]. Developed under the European Space Agency’s General Support Technology Program, LUMIO is led by Politecnico di Milano and supported by the Italian Space Agency, the Norwegian Space Agency, United Kingdom Space Agency, and Swedish National Space Agency.

Despite extensive ground-based campaigns of lunar impact flashes (LIF), the meteoroid flux on the Moon remains poorly assessed, particularly in the millimeter - to decimeter - size range [2]. LUMIO aims addressing this gap by continuously monitoring the entire far-side disk, extending ground-based observations, which are constrained to the Moon near-side and limited by weather conditions [3], and contributing to a more accurate characterization of the meteoroid population in the cislunar space.

The Mission : LUMIO is a 12U CubeSat that, after commissioning and a long transfer phase (~170 days) designed to minimize energy consumption, will operate for one year in a quasi-halo orbit around the Earth–Moon L2 Lagrangian point. At the end of its nominal mission, it will conclude operations by intentionally impacting the lunar surface, effectively becoming a LIF itself [4] (figure 1).

The operational phase will be alternately divided into a *Science Cycle* and a *Navigation & Engineering Cycle*. The Science Cycle will focus on LIF detection and will take place when the observed lunar disk is shadowed by more than a predefined percentage (~50%, TBC). The Navigation & Engineering

Cycle will serve for data downlink operations, routine spacecraft activities, and validating an autonomous navigation experiment aiming at autonomous localization of LUMIO relative to the Moon [5].

The instrument: The detection of LIFs will be carried out through LUMIO-Cam, an optical sensor operating in the visible to near-infrared spectral range (450–950 nm). By maintaining the entire lunar disk within its field of view (FoV), the instrument will continuously monitor the shadowed portion of the surface to detect impact flashes. Once an impact is detected, the frame containing the event—along with a TBD number of frames before and after the event—will be selected. For each of these frames, a small region of interest consisting of a few pixels surrounding the impact location will be extracted and saved. This payload will enable the quantification of the frequency, location, and energy of impacts, thereby improving existing models of the meteoroid flux in the cislunar environment [6].

Mission updates: LUMIO has entered in Phase C at the beginning of March 2026. During this 18-months phase, a detailed design of all the subsystem will be performed, including initial activities for manufacturing the spacecraft and the payload. On the science side, emphasis will be placed on the payload design, its performance assessment, and its in-flight operations

Four months after the Phase C kick off, we expect to have preliminary design results available, in particular for the payload. These will include the selection of the camera detector through a careful trade-off analysis between CCD and CMOS technologies.

Based on this decision, the selected camera performance parameters will be implemented in Astronomical Bodies Rendering Application for Mission design (ABRAM) [7], a physically-based radiometrically-consistent render engine, to generate datasets of synthetic lunar images and LIFs (figure 2). These datasets will be used for algorithm tests, for the design and validation of the data processing pipeline, and for science return quantification from the science team. Parallel to these activities, the in-flight camera operations will be refined, including assessing camera parameter selections via computer simulations.

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Figure 1. Overview of the LUMIO mission.

Figure 2. Example of a synthetic image of the Moon obtained via the ABRAM simulation tool, in the visual spectral range. The zoom image shows a lunar impact flash in larger scale.